

EVALUATION OF DIFFERENT INSECTICIDE MODULES AGAINST STEM BORERS OF SOYBEAN (*Glycine max.*)

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted during kharif 2021-22 on the field of Zonal Agricultural Research Station, Yavatmal Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidhyapeeth. The effect of different insecticide modules were assessed against stem borers of soybean. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with eight modules replicated thrice. Among them Module 7 (Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/l, fb Thiamethaxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit) followed by Module 6 (Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Thiacloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5 ml/lit fb Profenofos 50% EC @ 2ml/lit) were found significantly superior in recording lower percent infestation of girdle beetle and stem fly. No deleterious effect of insecticide modules was observed on lady bird beetle in soybean through out the season, all modules appeared safer in conservation of the natural enemy.

Key words: Girdle beetle, Insecticide modules, Lady bird beetle, Soybean, Stem fly, Yield

Introduction

Soybean (*Glycine max.*) is one of the most important leguminous crops. Soybean 'The miracle golden bean of 20th century' has revolutionized the agriculture as well as generated economy of many countries like China and Japan (Balasubharamaniam, 1972). Though soybean is a legume crop, yet it is widely used as oilseed. India is the fifth largest producer of soybean in the world after the USA, Brazil, Argentina and China (Sharma *et al.*, 2014). Nationally, it occupies an area of 108.395 lakh ha and production is 114.834 lakh MT. Maharashtra ranks first in soybean production in India 45.44 lakh MT and its area is 40.39 lakh ha. (Anonymous 2020). Various insects feed on soybean crop from germination to harvesting stage. Soybean crop average losses 20 to 25 per cent yield due to insect pests. Soybean crop recorded about 380 species of insects in many parts of the world. In Maharashtra 19 species of insects have been identified attacking this crop (Munde, 1982). Among them stem fly (*Melanagromyza sojae* Zehnter), girdle beetle (*Obereopsis brevis* Sweden board), tobacco caterpillar (*Spodoptera litura*), semiloopers (*Gasonia gemma*, *Achaea janata*, *Chrysodeixis acuta*) and sucking insect pests such as white fly (*Bemisia tabaci*), thrips and aphids are important. Singh and Singh (1990) recorded 30.26 per cent yield loss in soybean due to *M. sojae*on. Whereas, Ansari and Sharma (2005) observed 19.5 per cent to 30.72 per cent infestation of girdle beetle in soybean. Out of various methods of pest management, use of chemical insecticides is most preferred by the farmers as it gives quick visible effects and easily available. Every year new chemical insecticides are coming in market. Also, the manufacturers are bringing combination products of different insecticides from different

Treatment details:

insecticidal groups with different mode of actions. In such situations, it becomes necessary to evaluate the bio-efficacy of these products against the targeted pests and critically inspect for their adverse effects on the natural enemies of the pests as well as on the plant. By considering the above-mentioned facts, the present investigation was undertaken to evaluate different insecticide modules against stem bores of soybean.

Material and Methods

The present studies on the "Evaluation of different insecticide modules against major pests of soybean" was carried out during kharif- 2021 on the field of ZARS, Yavatmal, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidhyapeeth. The experiment was carried out in Randomized Block Design in order to test level of significance among the various treatments as per Gomez and Gomez (1984) with eight modules replicated thrice. The soybean Variety JS-335 was sown on 30th June 2021 with the gross plot size 4.5 m x 3.0 m and 3.6 m x 2.9 m net plot size. In modules 1, 2, 3 and 4 seed treatment of thiamethoxam 30 FS was taken first followed by first spray at 35 DAS and second spray at 15 days interval after first spray. In modules 5, 6 and 7 first spray was taken on 20 DAS and remaining two spray was taken at 15 days interval after each spray. The observations recorded during investigation were per cent infestation of stem fly and girdle beetle, and population of natural enemies lady bird beetle per meter row length were recorded. The yield data were also recorded at the time of threshing. The cumulative per cent infestation of stem fly and girdle beetle as well as average population of natural enemies per meter row length were worked out on the basis of average of all observations.

Treatment	Module Details
Module 1	Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8 ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Flubendiamide 20 WG @ 0.5 gm/lit.
Module 2	Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8 ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Indoxacarb 15.80% EC @ 0.66 ml/lit.
Module 3	Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 10 ml/kg of seeds fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit fb Lambda-cyhalothrin 4.90% CS @ 2 ml/lit.
Module 4	Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 10 ml/kg of seeds fb Thiacloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit.
Module 5	Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9 ml/lit fb Novaluron 6.25% SC + Indoxacarb 4.50% SC @ 1.75 ml/lit

Module 6	Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Thiachloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5 ml/lit fb Profenofos 50% EC @ 2ml/lit.
Module 7	Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Thiamethaxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit.
Module 8	Control (water spraying)

Result and Discussion

Cumulative effect of different insecticide modules against stem fly

The cumulative average per cent infestation of stem fly in all modules was significantly lower than the untreated control (9.09%) and ranges in 1.80 to 4.54 per cent (Table 1). The minimum cumulative average per cent infestation of stem fly was recorded in Module 7 comprising of Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Thiamethaxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit (1.80 %) at par with module 6 i.e. Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Thiachloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5 ml/lit fb Profenofos 50% EC @ 2ml/lit (2.78 %). The next effective module was Module 2 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Indoxacarb 15.80% EC @ 0.66 ml/lit (3.38 %) at par with Module 1 comprising of Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Flubendiamide 20 WG @ 0.5 gm/lit (3.45 %), Module 4 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30FS @ 10ml/kg of seeds fb Thiachloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit (4.11 %), Module 5 i.e. Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9 ml/lit fb Novaluron 6.25% SC + Indoxacarb 4.50% SC @ 1.75 ml/lit (4.22 %) and Module 3 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30FS @ 10ml/kg of seeds fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit fb Lambda-cyhalothrin 4.90% CS @ 2 ml/lit (4.54 %). Whereas, maximum per cent infestation of stem fly was recorded in untreated control (9.09 %). Above results are in confirmation with work carried out by Raut *et al.* (2014) who reported that, among the different insecticides tested Triazophos 40 EC @ 0.04% was successful treatment in minimizing the stem fly infestation in soybean however, this treatment was followed by Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 0.006 and Indoxacarb 15.8 EC @ 0.01%. Similarly, Patil and Phad (2014) reported that Triazophos 40 EC @ 800 ml/ha was found most superior in reducing the damage of both girdle beetle and stem fly in soybean followed by Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC.

Cumulative effect of different insecticide modules against girdle beetle

The data presented in Table 2 revealed that cumulative average per cent infestation of girdle beetle in all modules were significantly superior over control module and ranges between 1.53 % to 5.99 per cent. Minimum average cumulative per cent infestation of girdle beetle was recorded in module 7 (Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Thiamethaxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit) with 1.53 per cent and at par with module 6 (Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Thiachloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5 ml/lit fb Profenofos 50% EC @ 2ml/lit) (1.89%). The next best module was module 4 (Thiamethoxam 30FS @ 10ml/kg of seeds fb Thiachloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9 ml/lit) with 2.98 per cent infestation at par with module 1 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Flubendiamide 20 WG @ 0.5 gm/lit (2.98%), module 5 i.e. Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25

ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9 ml/lit fb Novaluron 6.25% SC + Indoxacarb 4.50% SC @ 1.75 ml/lit (3.08%), module 2 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Indoxacarb 15.80% EC @ 0.66 ml/lit (3.27%) and module 3 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30FS @ 10ml/kg of seeds fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit fb Lambda-cyhalothrin 4.90% CS @ 2 ml/lit (3.37%). The maximum 5.99 per cent infestation of girdle beetle was recorded in (module 8) i.e. untreated control.

The above results finds support in the research work carried out by Patel *et al.* (2019) reported that treatment sprays of Triazophos @ 320 g a.i./ha was found as the best treatment against Girdle beetle followed by Chlorantraniliprole @ 30 g a.i./ha. The earlier worker Punsiya (2017) reported that among the different insecticides tested against girdle beetle, Thiachloprid 21.7 SC was found effective followed by Betacyfluthrin 8.49% + Imidacloprid 19.81 OD % and pyriproxyfen 10 EC. Similarly, Kalyan and Ameta (2016) also reported that Triazophos 40 EC @ 1.25 L/ha and Thiamethoxam 25 WG @ 100 g/ha were effective against girdle beetle infestation.

Cumulative effect of different insecticide modules on lady bird beetle

The data on cumulative average lady bird beetle population (Table 3) recorded after treatment sprays found statistically non-significant. However, numerically lady bird beetle population was found maximum (2.79/mrl) in a module 8 (untreated control), while minimum lady bird beetle population (1.86/mrl) was recorded in module 6 (Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb. Thiachloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5 ml/lit fb Profenofos 50% EC @ 2ml/lit). The data revealed that treatment modules have shown their safety against lady bird beetle population.

The present findings are in confirmation with Raut *et al.* (2014) who reported that different insecticides tested viz., triazophos 40 EC @ 0.04%, chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 0.006 and indoxacarb 15.8 EC @ 0.01% were found safer to the predators in soybean ecosystem. Whereas, Bokan (2020) recorded maximum population of natural enemies on soybean in the plots treated with Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 SC followed by Spinetoram 11.7 SC, Indoxacarb 15.8 EC, Flubendiamide 39.35 SC, Emamectin benzoate 5 SG and Lambda cyhalothrin 4.9CS.

Effects of different insecticide modules on the yield of soybean

The data presented in Table 4 in respect of yield of soybean revealed that all modules tested under present study against stem bores of soybean produced significantly higher grain yield than untreated control (8.56 q/ha). Among the different treatments Module 7 comprising of Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Thiamethaxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit. produce highest yield (20.86 q/ha). Whereas, it was found at par with module 5 i.e. Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9 ml/lit fb Novaluron 6.25% SC + Indoxacarb 4.50% SC @ 1.75 ml/lit (19.21 q/ha) and module 2 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8 ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole 18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Indoxacarb 15.80% EC @ 0.66 ml/lit. (18.42 q/ha). The next effective module was module 1 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 8 ml/kg of seeds fb Chlorantroniliprole

18.50% SC @ 0.2 ml/lit fb Flubendiamide 20 WG @ 0.5 gm/lit. (17.89 q/ha) at par with modules 3 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 10 ml/kg of seeds fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit fb Lambda-cyhalothrin 4.90% CS @ 2 ml/lit. (17.38 q/ha), module 4 i.e. Thiamethoxam 30 FS @ 10 ml/kg of seeds fb Thiacloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5ml/lit fb Emamectin benzoate 1.90% EC @ 0.9ml/lit. (16.85 q/ha) and module 6 i.e. Thiamethoxam 12.60% ZC + Lambda-cyhalothrin 9.50% ZC @ 0.25 ml/lit fb Thiacloprid 21.71% EC @ 1.5 ml/lit fb Profenofos 50% EC @ 2ml/lit. (16.18 q/ha).

The present findings are in accordance with results obtained by earlier workers like Raut *et al.* (2014) who recorded maximum yield of soybean 22.54 q/ha with the treatment of Chlorantraniliprole 18.5% SC @ 0.06 %. at par with Triazophos 40 % EC @ 0.04 % and Indoxacarb 15.8% EC @ 0.01 %. Similar results were also obtained by Ilyas *et al.* (2015) who reported highest yield of soybean i.e 2061 kg/ha from plots treated with Triazophos 40 Ec @ 800 ml/ha followed by Chlorantraniliprole 18.5 Sc @ 150 ml/ha (1860 kg/ha) and Indoxacarb 14.5 SL @ 500 ml/ha (1836 kg/ha).

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Table 1: Cumulative effect of different insecticide modules against stem bores of soybean

Module	Cumulative per cent infestation of stem fly				Cumulative per cent infestation of girdle beetle				LLB / mrl	Yield (q/ha)
	3 DAT	7 DAT	14 DAT	Mean	3 DAT	7 DAT	14 DAT	Mean	Mean	
M1	2.89(1.69)	3.40(1.84)	4.05(2.00)	3.45(1.84)	2.21(1.48)	3.10(1.75)	3.65(1.90)	2.98(1.71)	2.25(1.57)	17.89
M2	2.76(1.65)	3.44(1.84)	3.95(1.98)	3.38(1.82)	2.54(1.57)	3.46(1.85)	3.82(1.94)	3.27(1.78)	2.29(1.59)	18.42
M3	3.85(1.95)	4.54(2.12)	5.23(2.28)	4.54(2.12)	2.57(1.59)	3.59(1.88)	3.94(1.97)	3.37(1.81)	2.54(1.67)	17.38
M4	3.32(1.82)	4.29(2.06)	4.72(2.16)	4.11(2.01)	2.06(1.42)	3.16(1.77)	3.73(1.91)	2.98(1.70)	1.97(1.46)	16.85
M5	3.51(1.86)	4.20(2.03)	4.95(2.20)	4.22(2.03)	2.15(1.41)	3.19(1.74)	3.90(1.92)	3.08(1.69)	1.90(1.42)	19.21
M6	2.20(1.47)	2.75(1.65)	3.38(1.83)	2.78(1.65)	1.42(1.18)	2.05(1.41)	2.19(1.47)	1.89(1.35)	1.86(1.40)	16.18
M7	1.47(1.21)	1.86(1.36)	2.08(1.43)	1.80(1.33)	1.11(1.05)	1.64(1.28)	1.85(1.35)	1.53(1.23)	2.05(1.49)	20.86
M8	8.60(2.91)	9.31(3.03)	9.37(3.05)	9.09(2.99)	5.05(2.22)	6.14(2.46)	6.78(2.57)	5.99(2.42)	2.79(1.76)	8.56
SE (m)±	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.09	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.13	0.97
CD at 5%	0.33	0.34	0.36	0.34	0.28	0.37	0.36	0.33	-	2.95
CV %	10.65	9.78	9.92	10.12	11.07	12.10	11.23	11.47		9.12

Note: Figures in parentheses are corresponding square root transformed values

DAT- Days after Treatment